

THE IMPACT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY ON MACROECONOMIC INDICATORS

SADRIDDINOV ULUGBEK JALOLIDDIN UGLI

Assistant, Department of International Financial Management, Samarkand Branch of ISFT

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19031798>

Аннотация. В данном исследовании на основе эмпирических данных изучается влияние развития цифровой экономики на макроэкономические показатели Узбекистана. Исследование проводится на основе панельных данных по 14 административным районам Узбекистана, а именно: 12 областям, 1 городу и 1 автономной республике. Модель изучает влияние индекса информационно-коммуникационных технологий (ИКТ), урбанизации, занятости, иностранных инвестиций и показателей внешней торговли как основных объясняющих факторов на рост валового регионального продукта регионов. Результаты модели МНК, использованной в исследовании, показывают, что развитие цифровой инфраструктуры в стране оказывает положительное влияние на экономический рост, а также значимость других переменных.

Ключевые слова: ИКТ, цифровая экономика, макроэкономические показатели, Узбекистан.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot ishida raqamli iqtisodiyot rivojlanishini O‘zbekistonning makroiqtisodiy ko‘rsatkichlariga ta’siri empirik ma’lumotlar asosida o‘rganilib chiqiladi. Tadqiqot ishi O‘zbekistonning 14 ta boshqaruv hududi, ya’ni 12 ta viloyat, 1 ta shahar va 1 ta avtonom Respublikaning panel ma’lumotlariga asoslanib olib boriladi. Modelda asosiy tushuntiruvchi omil sifatida axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari (AKT) indeksi, urbanizatsiya, bandlik, xorijiy investitsiyalar va tashqi savdo ko‘rsatkichlari hududlarning yalpi hududiy mahsuloti o‘shiga ta’siri o‘rganiladi. Tadqiqotda qo‘llanilgan OLS modelining natijalari mamlakatdagi raqamli infratuzilma rivojlanishining iqtisodiy o‘shiga ijobiy ta’sir qilishini ko‘rsatib, qolgan o‘zgaruvchilarning ham ahamiyati muhimligini ko‘rsatadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: O‘zb: AKT, raqamli iqtisodiyot, makroiqtisodiy ko‘rsatkichlar, O‘zbekiston. Eng: ICT, digital economy, macroeconomic indicators, Uzbekistan. Рус: ИКТ, цифровая экономика, макроэкономические показатели, Узбекистан

Annotation. This research study examines the impact of digital economy development on macroeconomic indicators of Uzbekistan based on empirical data. The research is conducted based on panel data from 14 administrative regions of Uzbekistan, namely 12 regions, 1 city and 1 autonomous republic. The model studies the impact of the information and communication technology (ICT) index, urbanization, employment, foreign investment and foreign trade indicators as the main explanatory factors on the growth of the gross regional product of the regions. The results of the OLS model used in the study show that the development of digital infrastructure in the country has a positive impact on economic growth, and the importance of other variables is also significant.

Keywords: ICT, digital economy, macroeconomic indicators, Uzbekistan.

Introduction. In today's globalized era, digital transformation has become an important factor not only for technological innovation, but also for sustainable economic development. Today, world experience shows that the widespread and widespread use of ICT allows for increased labor productivity, reduced transaction costs, and the formation of new market segments.

In Uzbekistan, the expansion of the digital economy is also one of the top priorities of state policy. That is why the “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” strategy has been developed, within the framework of which large-scale work is being carried out to increase the digital potential of all regions and modernize all sectors of the economy. However, it is worth noting that certain differences still remain between digital infrastructure and economic development in different regions. The relevance of this study is that it assesses the extent to which digital economy indicators in regions can affect the region's gross domestic product. The purpose of the study is to identify correlation and regression relationships between the digital economy and economic indicators based on statistical data for the period 2010-2024. This, of course, can serve as a scientifically sound source for developing and optimizing future digitalization policies.

Literature review

The study of the impact of digital infrastructure and the development of the digital economy on the economic growth of countries is one of the central issues of modern economic research today. Because the processes of digital transformation have been proven in studies to ensure economic efficiency in several strategic areas. For example, digitization processes not only allow to increase the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and sharply reduce corruption, but it is noted that the digital transaction sector accounts for a significant part of GDP, especially in countries [1]. Some studies have shown that the expansion of the digital economy, when focusing on regional development, can increase economic efficiency, rational use of available resources, and ensure social justice. In particular, the development of e-commerce and similar services will help local entrepreneurs access global markets and increase their income, leading to an increase in employment in the country [2].

In addition, Khabibullaev (2024) emphasizes the importance of introducing technologies such as artificial intelligence, blockchain, and IT, developing infrastructure in the country, increasing digital literacy, and improving the regulatory framework in the development of the digital economy [3]. Some scientific studies have shown that creating incentives for the development of the digital economy creates conditions for entrepreneurship and innovation. That is, it is emphasized that state support in this regard is especially important for the development of small and medium-sized businesses [4]. Farmonov emphasized the great role of the digital economy and technological development as the main factors influencing the growth and global integration of the national economy [5]. Levent Ozdemir (2024) in his research paper, using panel data from 158 countries around the world, has shown that the development of the level of ICT has a significant impact on economic growth while maintaining the financial stability of countries [6].

Research methodology

In this research, the impact of the development of the digital economy on the level of economic development for 14 regions of Uzbekistan was empirically analyzed based on panel data of the regions for the period 2010-2024. The study estimated the following econometric model using the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method:

$$\ln gdp_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ICT_index_{it} + \beta_2 urbanization_{it} + \beta_3 employment_{it} + \beta_4 fdi_{it} + \beta_5 trit_{it} + \beta_6 FTT_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

The description of the variables is as follows:

- $\log(gdp)$: Dependent variable – Logarithmic value of gross regional product.
- ICT_index : The main independent variable – ICT index, which represents the level of digitalization of regions.
- $urbanization$: Level of urbanization.

- employment: Share of the population employed in the economy.
- log_fdi, trade_openness and log_trade_volume: Logarithmic indicators of foreign direct investment, trade openness and foreign trade turnover.
- where i – region, t – time.
- ε_{it} – random error term.

To ensure the accuracy of the model, some variables were presented in logarithmic values. Analyses were performed using Stata software.

Results

In Table 1 of the study, the following results were obtained using the OLS econometric model: the ICT index, which is the main independent variable in the model, is statistically significant in both estimation methods and has a positive coefficient. That is, an increase in the ICT index by one unit ensures an increase in the gross regional product by 0.55 points. This result is fully consistent with the scientific evidence in the existing literature that the widespread implementation of digital technologies increases overall efficiency and leads to economic growth.

Table 1. The impact of the digital economy and macroeconomic factors on log GDP (OLS results)

	(1)	(2)
	log_gdp	log_gdp
ICT_index	0.554*** (0.036)	0.563*** (0.036)
urbanization	-0.005*** (0.002)	
employment	0.008* (0.004)	-0.006 (0.004)
log_fdi	0.148*** (0.019)	0.151*** (0.018)
trade_opennes	-0.510*** (0.159)	
log_FTT	0.230*** (0.026)	0.148*** (0.023)
_cons	7.342*** (0.393)	8.374*** (0.283)
R2	0.963	0.953
Observations	225	225

Standard errors in parentheses
* $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

Source: Author’s calculation

Our estimation model showed that all independent variables in the model have different effects on the growth of the gross regional product of the regions. For example, urbanization has a very strong statistical significance, but has a negative coefficient. This can be mainly explained by the concentration of regional resources or the pressure on infrastructure. Although the employment rate also has a positive statistical significance in our first estimation method, the second model has lost its significance. That is, its impact on economic growth is not stable. It can be seen that foreign direct investment and trade volume in the model have a positive coefficient and are statistically significant at 1%. These results indicate that they play an important role in increasing the volume of regional production. The last independent variable, trade openness, had a negative coefficient in our first model, which may be due to the differences in trade volumes and their structural differences in our regions. The level of explanation of our estimation method is 96%, indicating that the variables used in this model can explain a large part of the changes in economic activity.

Conclusion and recommendations

This study empirically analyzed how the growth of the digital economy in the regions of Uzbekistan affects the volume of gross regional product, which is the main macroeconomic indicator of the country, using panel data. The main independent variable in the model, the ICT index, and the control variables, foreign investment and gross trade turnover, were shown to be important factors stimulating economic activity. The unstable effects of the remaining variables indicate the existence of differences in regional economic structures.

Therefore, based on the above results, it was considered appropriate to state the following recommendations.

1. Expand ICT coverage to reduce the digitalization gap between our regions.
2. Ensure greater economic growth by directing foreign investments into the country not only to the industrial sector, but also to high-tech and digital services.
3. In order to achieve the above recommendations smoothly, it is possible to achieve this by training specialists with ICT skills. This will increase the qualitative share of the employment factor in economic growth.

Overall, the research suggests that the growth of the digital economy can be an important factor in shaping regional economic policy. Future studies using other assessment methods and data may shed more light on this area.

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